

Actual vs Predicted (MaxTemp)

Standardized Residuals (MaxTemp)

Partial Regression Plot (MaxTemp)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2744$$

Interpretation:

- 1 = positive autocorrelation**
- 2 = no autocorrelation**
- 4 = negative autocorrelation**

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 11.6875

p-value: 0.0006

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

White Test

White Statistic: 14.3131

df: 2

p-value: 0.0008

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

Histogram of Residuals (MaxTemp)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – MaxTemp

